

BIGSTUFF IN A SMALL COUNTRY. EXPERIENCES OF CONSERVATION OF LARGE SIZE INDUSTRIAL HERITAGE IN BELGIUM

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From the years 1970 onwards, the notorious regionalisation and the outlines of the federal State got gradually clear form in Belgium. In 1989, the metropolitan region of Brussels (beside the Flemish region and the Walloon region) becomes a full third Belgian region. These regions and the three "language-communities" (the Flemish Community, the French Community and the German Community) have adopted different views and policies with regard to cultural matters, included the industrial heritage, which comes into sight through different approaches, legislations, money flows and attainments.

The different policies in the Belgian regions and communities concerning industrial heritage reflect partly their economic history. The traditional Walloon coal, glass, iron and steel industry (all providing large scale equipment) is quite different compared to the small and medium familial companies have predominated the economy in Flanders for a very long time. The industrial heritage in Flanders is, in general, more spread over, of a smaller scale, and more heterogeneous than in Wallonia. In Flanders, sub-regions with former mono-industries (such as the brick-industry in the Rupe-region, the coalmining in Limburg, the flax-industry around the city of Kortrijk and along the river Leie) were more exceptions than the rule.

For a more detailed analysis on this topic, see our recent contribution, published in the review "Industrial Patrimony : resources, practices, cultures" (1).

Lets' try now to give a brief (and incomplete) overview of concrete realisations in the field of the big scale industrial heritage in the different parts of the country.

BRUSSELS

Huge restoration projects are quite marginal. For example, it was not possible to preserve (even partially) the impressive heritage of the "Cokeries de Marly" in the Brussels-harbour. Nice exceptions of renovation of some spectacular industrial heritage sites should be mentioned, all resulting of public-private-partnership operations. The reuse of the Royal Warehouses "Tour & Taxis", turned into a complex of offices, restaurants and shops and the "Entrepot B" (with exceptional shed-structure), reused as multi purpose event hall, are the first succesful steps of the "Tour & Taxis"-transport and commerce site renovation (2). Another recent renovated big scale building is the former Wielemans-Ceuppens brewery, reused since very recently as contemporary art centre (3).

During recent years the Royal Greenhouses of Laken (4), open to the public every year in may, underwent a gradual restoration, in strong contrast with the bad maintenance and poor condition of several glass houses in the "Nationale Plantentuin" (National Botanic Gardens) at Meise (in Flanders), one of the few scientific or cultural institutions still financed by the federal government.

FLANDERS

Flanders has a very varied industrial heritage (5). The small scale sites and structures are predominant and this peculiar situation leads to a fragmentation of local and regional heritage initiatives. Very few of the older big scale industrial structures have survived : space is a precious good in the very densely populated Flemish region !

Near Kortrijk, the former electric power station of Zwevegem, now a public property and under restoration as art centre and cultural equipment, is a good example. In the surroundings of Kortrijk, the brickyards and tile-production culminated in the interwar-period. Some dry-sheds were renovated as shops, as can be experienced at the Pottelberg-site, conserving also a power hall with steam engines, forming part now

of the scenery of a local restaurant : although the renovation is not very respectful, the contrast of "Pottelberg" with the ruins and derelict sheds of "Koramic" & "Le Littoral" in the same town as surprising. In Antwerp, the Central Railway Station (6) underwent a meticulous restoration, with its "hidden" underground adaptation as shopping area and "high speed train"-platforms.

Other interesting large scale structures are located in de old harbour district. Since 2006 the monumental "Sint-Felix warehouse" is the new location of the municipal archives. In the immediate surroundings, on the west side of the Kattendijkdok, are located : the 19th Century dry-docks (still in use nowadays). Nearby is the Montevideo warehouse (not yet renovated).

The old port of Antwerp is a huge open air museum of transport heritage (7), considering the importance of the Mexico bridges, the weigh bridge Siberia, rare types of pumping houses, old examples of (listed) harbour cranes along the river Scheldt, the "Royerssluis" (a rare lock dating from the beginning of the 20th C, hydraulic power stations as the "Zuiderpershuis", now a multicultural theatre (8).

Meanwhile a brand new museum about the history of city and harbour, the so called "MAS" (Museum on the River) is under construction in between the oldest docks, dating from the beginning of the 19th C (9). The new museum will focus also on the recent history, popular culture and actual developments, as on the threat of destruction of villages like Kallo or Doel, due to the extension of the left bank harbour of Antwerp.

Despite big efforts of the local actors, very few remains of the world famous, once a time 15 kilometres long row of brickyards in the Rupel region and the town of Boom. Most interesting conservation area is the district of Noeveren, where the "ecomuseum" EMABB (Ecomuseum and Archive of the Boom Brickyards) is located, underlining during the guided tours the social life and work of the local community (10).

The "Vaartkom" in Leuven with the old and more recent brewery buildings of Artois (nowadays "InBev") is a nice example of a inner harbour under permanent redevelopment through 2,5 Centuries. The whole site is threatened now with demolition, with exception of the (listed) Mills Van Orshoven, partly rented by SIWE, a platform in Flanders for associations in the field of industrial and scientific heritage (11).

Perhaps the best example of "bigstuff industrial heritage" in Flanders is the legacy of the Flemish coalmines, all dating from the beginning of the 20th Century (12). After the closing of the last mines (1989-1992), the most representative mining heritage elements were listed and restored with government support. In the Beringen-mine, the best conserved mine as a whole, we find nowadays the "Vlaams Mijnmuseum" (Flemish mining museum), a modest initiative supported by volunteers and municipal funds, waiting for a more professional extension over the whole site.

Several mining buildings of the Zolder coalmine were renovated for new uses (second hand shops, training centre for unemployed workers (in the former Electricity-hall), a centre for ecological construction, restaurant, etc. In between these buildings a new market place was created, used also for different public events. In Winterslag, the oldest (1917) and last constructed (1967) mine tower coexist. Part of the administration building is used as offices and as a cinema, but the heart of the mine, the machine hall and power house, are kept in their original state and often used for wedding parties and other social events. In Eisden, a abusively demolished (listed) mine tower has been (badly) reconstructed. The prestigious mine buildings are used as municipal art academy and music school, as a hotel, a cinema and an outlet centre (conceived as a postmodern shopping village). In Waterschei only the exterior part of some important mine buildings are renovated, many plans came not true until now.

We insist on the impressive size and scale of the coalmine - garden cities (good examples of "company towns"), with their schools, huge churches, casinos, etc., all of very high standards and architectural quality, considering the construction period, some 80 years ago.

To complete this overview, lets mention a recent legislation "Decreet varend erfgoed", approved by the Flemish Government, concerning the conservation of sailing heritage, applicable to still used boat and ships. Another new legislation about the future legal protection of airplanes, trains and cars is under preparation now (13).

WALLONIA

It is hard to imagine that so very few large scale artefacts of the heavy industry have been preserved from total destruction (14). For example, absolutely nothing remains nowadays of the legendary 19th and 20th Century glass industry in and around the city of Charleroi, Jumet and Lodelinsart.

The conservation efforts orientated towards the coal extraction heritage. This can be partly explained by the high degree of "emotional value" of the mine labour, but also by the extraordinary quality of some sites in Wallonia. "Le Grand Hornu", near Mons is the most visited site, reused for a the walloon Museum of Contemporary Arts (MAC'S) and Design gallery "Grand Hornu images" (15).

Only ten kilometres from there, in Frameries, the Crachet-coalmine was transformed by the French architect Jean Nouvel as "Parc d'Aventures Scientifiques" (PASS), a science centre orientated to young visitors (16). In Péronnes-lez-Binche, a huge washing plant of the 1950 is actually under transformation as a walloon Archive Centre. The mine village of Bois-du-Luc (near La Louvière) is perhaps the best conserved, most complete and most authentic (still occupied) mid 19th Century coalmining site (17). The industrial buildings are well restored and managed by the « Ecomusée régional du Centre ».

About 20 km more eastwards is the industrial town of Charleroi. In the colliery of "Le Bois du Cazier", in the suburb of Marcinelle, major accidents occurred (the 8th of august 1956 and next days 262 miners died, following a short-circuit and devastating fire). The winding engine room of this mine has become a remarkable memorial, forming part of the "Museum of Walloon Industry" (18). Other remains of mining are spread all over the agglomeration : the pithead gears of "Le Pechon" in Couillet, tip heaps in Châtelet. These are examples of isolated, listed monuments but without conservation of educational links...

The same can be said about the (very rarely conserved) coal monuments in the surroundings of Liège (19). Since more than twenty years the ruins of "Le Charbonnage du Hasard"-colliery at Cheratte are waiting for an investor and a suitable rehabilitation project. Not the Cheratte-colliery but (only 6 kilometres from there) the more recent and not so outstanding colliery of Argenteau, located on the heights of Blegny, has been developed as main tourist attraction of the region. Because of their high position in the topography of the region, these galleries are permanently drained without major technical efforts into the Meuse-valley. This is the reason why visitors can explore some of the underground coal galleries. "Blegny Trembleur" is the only place in Belgium where visitors can do so (20).

"Tip heaps" are better known as "terris" in Belgium. In Wallonia more than 300 terrils remains after the closing of the last mines in 1984. "Espace Terrils" is the name of an association who organises all kind of cultural and sport events related to the terrils. They helped to realise the "Sentier des Terrils", a signposted footpath of 280 km long, crossing over and along the most important tip heaps, the so called "transterrienne walk" (21). Many recent publications deal with the ecological value and natural beauty of the black mountains, changed in nature reserves and even in vineyards ! (22)

The "crown jewel" of big stuff around 1900 in Wallonia is the ensemble of four hydraulic ships elevators on the "Canal du Centre" (mentioned since about ten years on the "Unesco World Heritage List"). They are an important part a unique canal landscape, including all kind of bridges, viaducts, even strange barracks and "la Cantine des Italiens", poor quality temporary constructions, occupied in the 1950 and 1960 by Italian immigrants, working in the blast furnaces Boël in La Louvière. The Unesco nomination confirmed that there was no longer risk of destruction of the old elevators after the construction of the world biggest ship elevator in Strépy-Thieu (in operation since 2002) : both engineering masterpieces are visited yearly by ten thousands of tourists and a different boat tours proposes the discovery of the elevators in combination with other canal engineering works at the "Plan incliné" at Ronquières, built in the 1960. Are these expensive infrastructures have as much value from economic point of view and as tourist attractions (23).

One of the most dramatic industrial landscapes of Wallonia (and western Europe) is the concentration of metallurgy factories in Marchienne-au-Pont (Charleroi), almost all belonging now to Arcelor (24). Part of the industrial installations are obsolete and there is no hope that representative parts we be saved from massive destruction. The actual politics will erase the black image of industrial past, often associated with corruption, crime, unemployment and other social problems. In the same agglomeration of Charleroi,

marked by a great variety of old industrial sites, one can find impressive old quarries, as for example in Montigny-le-Tilleuil

The city of Liège has an interesting amount of industrial and technological monuments. One example is de "Pont de la Fragnée", created for the 1905 World Exhibition, decorated with a monumental sculpture group dedicated to Zénobe Gramme, inventor of the dynamo. At the south western and northern outskirts of the agglomeration one can observe along the Meuse river the monumental industrial landscapes of Cockerill-Ougrée, the Cockerill-Iron foundry at Seraing (with the HF 6, out of use since april 2005), the Chertal rolling mill at Herstal. All these installations are property now of Arcelor and the future of this heavy is very uncertain (25).

About 25 km east of Liège is located the city of Verviers, once the most important wool manufacturing centre of Europe (26). The city experienced a deep economic crisis during the sixties and seventies, when nearly all mills closed down. One of the oldest wool spinning mills is the Simonis-factory (also called "Le Chat"), reused since more than twenty years for social housing. Some of the old textile factories are decorated with symbols of the wool and large scale machinery to process the wool are displayed all over the city, as washing installations, put in front of the "Maison Bonvoisin", a house belonging to an early industrial wool baron.

The history of the Verviers wool industry can be experienced in the "Centre de la Laine et de la Mode" installed in the former "Usine Bettonville". Verviers renovated one of the oldest working houses district (1800-1810), "les Grande rames", still used for social housing. The textile legacy of Verviers is spread also at the outskirts of town and in the surrounded villages, like Pépinster and mostly located along the river Vesder. There is a lot of cooperation in the Euregio Verviers – Aachen (with support of European funds), also in the promotion of industrial heritage tourism.

To end our brief travel through "big stuff industrial heritage" in Wallonia, we mention the "Schieferstollen" (or 'Slate mines') at Recht, a mining-village situated German speaking Belgium. A 19th C. slate mine was opened in Recht very recently for visitors, who are invited to explore a labyrinth of caves caused by rude labour and long human (mostly manual) efforts (27).

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this brief sketch about "big stuff" industrial heritage in Belgium is clear : despite some isolated efforts to save large (mostly appealing and prestigious) industrial building and / or machinery, the actual situation is disappointing. One can notice a lack of global public policy in these matters. Urban planning priorities and the constant need of space of develop old industrial places for new economic, traffic of recreational purposes are very clear in each of the three Belgian regions. The stock-capacity for the conservation of huge industrial equipment in the few industrial museums is also very limited. Meanwhile it is important to record threatened sites by all means possible iconographic / photographic databases, oral history projects, saving company-archives, etc.

NOTES

- 1. VIAENE Patrick, Some particularities in the industrial history of Belgium, in relation to actual approaches to the industrial heritage movement. In : Patrimoine de l'Industrie / Industrial Patrimony, 2007, nr. 17, p. 43-47.
- 2. See : VANDERHULST Guido, a.o., Tour & Taxis, a district in motion. Brussels, (La Fonderie) 2000. www.t&t.com
- 3. See : DALED J. a. o., Blomme / Wiels. Brussel, 2007. www.wiels.org
- 4. GOEDLEVEN Edgard, De Koninklijke Serres te Laken. The Royal Greenhouses at Laeken. Tielt, (Lannoo) 1997.
- 5. For a general overview, see : VIAENE Patrick, Industriële archeologie in België. Gent, (Stichting Mens & Cultuur) 1990. See also : VIAENE Patrick, Le patrimoine industriel en Flandre. In : Industrial Patrimony, nr. 16, p. 55-71.
- 6. See : DE SOMER Patricia, DE SMET Gaston, Het Centraal Station te Antwerpen, een levend monument. Antwerpen, (Stedelijke Dienst Monumentenzorg) 1986.
- 7. A marvellous overview of the port heritage can be found in a recent publication : VAN HOOYDONCK Eric, VERHOEVEN Patrick, The ports portable. A cultural travel guide to the port cities of Antwerp, Hamburg & Rotterdam. Antwerpen, (Pandora) 2007.
- 8. See : HILMER Albert, Het Zuiderpershuis en de zeven andere hydraulische stations in Antwerpen. In : Monumenten en Landschappen, Jr. 4, nr. 6 (december 1985), p. 8-28.
- 9. For more information about "Museum aan de Stroom", see : www.mas.be
- 10. EMABB, Noeveren 196 Boom, www.emabb.be
- 11. SIME is an association for industrial & scientific heritage in Flanders & Brussels. info@sive.be / www.sive.be
- 12. See : VAN DOORSLAER, Een eeuw Steenkool in Limburg. Tielt, (Lannoo) 1992.
- 13. These legislations are initiated and prepared by thematic overviews by VCM (Vlaamse Contactcommissie Monumentenzorg - Forum voor Erfgoedverenigingen), www.vcmcontactforum.be
- 14. The best overview is until now is : GENICOT Luc-Fr., GAIER Claude, Wallonie-Bruxelles : Berceau de l'industrie sur le continent européen. Louvain-la-Neuve, (PIWB / UCL) 1990. See also : VERCHEVAL-VERVOORT J., L'héritage des gueules noires. Charleroi, (Les Archives de Wallonie) 1994.
- 15. MAC's, rue Sainte-Louise, 82, B-7031 Hornu.
- 16. The « PASS » is situated in the south western outskirts of Mons.
- 17. Ecomusée du Bois-de-Luc, rue Saint-Patrice 2b, B 7110 La Louvière.
- 18. See : www.leboisducazier.be / Adress : rue du Cazier 80, B 6001 Marcinelle.
- 19. GAIER Claude, Huit siècles de houillerie Liégeoise. Liège, (Editions du Perron) 1988.
- 20. Blegny-Mine : 23 rue L. Marlet, B-4670 Blegny. domaine@blegny.be
- 21. Topo-Guide de Sentier de Grande Randonnée. Sentier des Terrils GR 412 Ouest & Topo-Guide de Sentier de Grande Randonnée. Sentier des Terrils GR 412 Est. (2007). See also : www.grsentiers.org
- 22. RAES Françoise, BOSTEELS Emmanuel, Terrils, de l'or noir à l'or vert. Brussels, (Racine) 2006.
- 23. See : www.hainauttourisme.be
- 24. For a thematic overview, see : VERCHEVAL-VERVOORT Jeanne, Les Sidérurgistes. Charleroi, (Les Archives de Wallonie) 1989.
- 25. See : DRICOT Th., Le Haut-Fourneau n° 6 de Seraing. La dernière coulée. Seraing, (Pixels Editions) 2006.
- 26. See : BAUWENS Catherine, Le patrimoine industriel de la region Verviétoise. Dison, Fondation Ad. Hardy) 1994.
- 27. About mining and stone extraction (general) see : STEVENS Luc, La Belgique Souterraine. Un monde fabuleux sous vos pieds. Brussels, (Labor) 2005